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Enhancing Students' Interest in Citizenship Education via the Use of Collaborative Instructional Strategy in Colleges of Education in Kogi State, Nigeria

Salome Mercy IDOKO

Department of General Studies, Nigeria Korea Friendship Institute of Vocational and Advanced
Technology Lokoja, Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of collaborative instructional strategy on students' interest in Citizenship Education in Colleges of Education in Kogi State, Nigeria. Three research questions and two hypotheses were developed to guide the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental design. The population of the study was 800 NCE II students of Citizenship Education in Colleges of Education in the State. Through balloting, Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa, with 140 NCE II students of Citizenship Education was assigned to collaborative instructional strategy while Federal College of Education, Okene, with 160 NCE II students of Citizenship Education was assigned to conventional method. The instrument for data collection was 30 – item Citizenship Education Interest Scale (CEIS). The instrument was validated by three experts and the reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha formula in which a coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Data collected were analysed

using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the results, the study revealed that the students taught Citizenship Education with collaborative instructional strategy had significantly higher mean interest ratings than the conventional group taught with lecture method. The study also found that gender of the students had no significant interaction effects with the treatment administered. Based on these findings, the study among others recommended that teachers at all levels of education should adopt collaborative instructional strategy for effective teaching and learning and seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized by states and federal ministries of education where teachers and lecturers will be taught the usage and application of modern instructional techniques such as collaborative instructional strategy.

Keywords: Citizenship Education, Collaborative Instructional Strategy, Interest, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Colleges of Education are tertiary institutions established to provide knowledge and skills to students who have passed through post-primary school education (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2014). The institutions are established to equip and train teachers for their functions in teaching profession (Excellence and Education Network, 2014). Onyesom (2013) stressed that students in Colleges of Education are exposed to the course such as Citizenship Education.

Citizenship Education encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for individuals to become informed, responsible and active citizens (Aliyu, 2016). The author maintained that the subject teaches individuals about their country's political, social, and legal systems and the principles of democracy, human rights, social justice and global citizenship. Bolaji (2020) described Citizenship Education as a subject which involves developing the knowledge, skills and confidence to enable people make their own decisions and to take responsibility for their own lives and communities. It is a statutory subject in the national curriculum.

Unfortunately, the turnout of results of NCE students of Citizenship Education in Colleges of Education in Kogi State, Nigeria as observed is not encouraging. The poor achievement of students in the course is worst. It is a worrisome issue that has attracted major stakeholders in Kogi State, Nigeria. The observed poor performance of the students could be linked with ineffective teaching and the outcome of the conventional teaching method mostly used for instructional delivery which worsen students' interest in learning. Akinbola (2019) noted that the use of poor teaching method is responsible for the students' poor achievement. Okon (2022) observed that conventional teaching methods are not challenging enough to the needs of the students. However, Barnstein (2016) stated that modern teaching methods are more effective and interactive. Abdullahi (2018) maintained that modern teaching methods require less talk on the part of the teacher and more contributions and activities from the students. Therefore, this study aims at testing the effectiveness of collaborative instructional strategy as a modern teaching strategy on students' interest.

Collaborative instructional strategy was proposed by Bakka, Tinzamn , Jones, Fine and Pierce in 1990 in America (Gaith, 2016). Okonkwo (2014) defined collaborative instructional strategy as a kind of instruction which involves instructors and a group of students working together to maximize learning. Learners attain their goals through collaboration and interdependence with one another. Oguche (2020) opined that collaborative instructional strategy is a programme in which students work in small groups to help one another master academic content. Sabaru (2014) expressed that collaborative instructional strategy involves students' participation in small group learning activities that promote positive interaction. Operationally, collaborative instructional strategy is defined as a teaching arrangement in which students are giving the opportunity to interact with one another in the teaching and learning process under the auspices of the lecturer. It is a heterogenous group instruction which is learner-centred approach. Adekola (2014) maintained that the strategy is a pedagogical approach that promotes students to students' interaction through working in small groups to maximize their learning and reach their goals for higher interest.

Interest is a subjective feeling of concentration or persisting tendency to pay attention and enjoy some activities or contents (Imoko & Agwagah, 2014). It is defined as likes and dislikes or one's preference and aversion. Adeosun (2019) emphasized that students' interest in Citizenship Education may be influenced by gender.

Gender refers to all the characteristics of male and female which describes behaviours or attributes expected of individuals on the basis of being either a male or female in a society. Irrespective of gender, the observed poor interest of NCE II students in Citizenship Education is worrisome and calls for immediate attention. One of the proven ways of finding solution to the problems could be by stimulating their interest in learning using more interactive methods (Gana, 2013). It is based on this background that this study was carried out to establish enhancing students' interest in Citizenship Education via the use of collaborative instructional strategy in colleges of Education in Kogi State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The interest of students in Citizenship Education in Kogi State Colleges of Education has been poor. The poor interest which resulted in poor achievement of NCE II students could be attributed to the lecturers' continuous use of lecture-based method of instruction. As a result, the students became discouraged, bored and inattentive while Citizenship Education lesson was going on with the assumption that Citizenship Education is difficult to learn. The problem of the study put in question form is: What is the effect of Collaborative Instructional strategy on students' interest in Citizenship Education in Kogi State Colleges of Education, Kogi State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on students' interest in Citizenship Education in Kogi State Colleges of Education, Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. determine whether Collaborative Instructional Strategy in teaching Citizenship Education enhanced Students' Interest.
- ii. find out the Effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy on Male and Female Students' Interest in Citizenship Education.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

- i. What are the mean interest ratings of NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy and those taught with the Conventional Method?
- ii. What are the mean interest ratings of Male and Female NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy?
- iii. What is the interaction effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy on the students' mean interest ratings in Citizenship Education?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- i. There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of NCE II students taught Citizenship Education with Collaborative Instructional Strategy and Conventional Method.
- ii. There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of Male and Female NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy.

Methodology

The design of the study was quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, a non-randomized pre-test post-test design was adopted. The reason was the fact that intact classes were used. The study was carried out in Kogi State College of Education, Ankpa and Federal College of Education, Okene, Kogi State, Nigeria. The population of the study was 800 NCE II of 2023/2024 session comprising 450 male and 350 female students. The sample of the study was three hundred (300) NCE II students (comprising 155 male and 145 female) selected from two Colleges of Education in Kogi State. Out of this, 140 students consisting of 80 male and 60 female were used in the experimental group while 160 students consisting of 90 male and 70 female were used in control group. Two Colleges of Education were purposively selected for the study and random sampling technique was used to assign each of the schools to experimental and control groups. The instrument for data collection was Citizenship Education Interest Scale (CEIS). It is made up of 30-item statements. The instrument was face validated by three experts, two from General Studies in Education (GSE) Department, Kogi State College of Education Ankpa and one from the same Department, Federal College of Education, Okene. Cronbach Alpha formula was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument which gave the reliability coefficient of 0.85. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA).

Results

Results of the study is presented according to research questions posed and the hypotheses formulated.

Research Question One

What are the mean interest ratings of NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy and those taught with Conventional Method?

Table 1: Means and Standard Deviations of students' Responses on Citizenship Education Rating Scale (CEIS)

Group	N	Pre – CEIS		Post- CEIS	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Experimental	160	2.50	1.32	3.75	1.60
Control	140	2.41	1.43	2.54	1.82
Mean Diff.		0.09		1.21	
Total	300				

The result presented in Table 1 shows that in Pre-CEIS, the experimental group had a mean interest rating of 2.50 with a standard deviation of 1.32, while the control group had a mean interest rating 2.41 with a standard deviation of 1.43. Also, the result shows that the mean interest ratings of the experimental group in Post-CEIS is 3.75 with a standard deviation of 1.60 while the mean interest ratings in the control group is 2.54 with a standard deviation of 1.82. The mean difference in the Pre-CEIS between the experimental and the control group is 0.09 while in Post-CEIS, it is 1.21. This indicates that Collaborative Instructional strategy improved students' interest in Citizenship Education.

Research Question Two

What are the mean interest ratings of male and female NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy?

Table 2: Means and Standard Deviations of Male and Female Students' Responses on Citizenship Education Interest Scale (CEIS) in the Experimental Group

Group	N	Pre- CEIS		Post- CEIS	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Male	80	2.74	1.62	3.60	1.27
Female	60	2.73	0.92	3.60	1.57
Mean Diff.		0.01		0.00	
Total	140				

The outcomes in Table 2 show that in Pre-CEIS, the mean interest rating of male students in experimental group was 2.74 with standard deviation of 1.62 while the mean interest ratings of the female students was 2.83 with the standard deviation of 0.82. In the Post-

CEIS the mean interest ratings of the male students was 3.60 with the standard deviation of 1.27 while the female students mean interest rating was 3.60 with the standard deviation of 1.57. The male and female students' Pre-CEIS mean interest rating difference was 0.01 whereas in their Post-CEIS the mean interest rating difference was 0.00.

Research Hypothesis One

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of students taught Citizenship Education with Collaborative Instructional Strategy and Conventional Method.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance of Experimental and Control Groups in Citizenship Education Interest Scale (CEIS)

Source	Type III Sum of sq	df	Mean Sq.	F	Sig.	Partial Eta sq
Corr Model	645.318 ^a	2	312.105	134.231	.000	.529
Intercept	574.820	1	574.820	235.721	.000	.600
Pre-CEIS	37.512	1	37.512	17.330	.000	.064
Group	599.213	1	599.213	280.643	.000	.637
Error	352.885	297	2.005			
Total	1100123.000	300				
Corrected Total	1023.221	299				

R Squared = .529 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.524)

Table 3 shows that the analysis of covariance mean interest ratings of students taught Citizenship Education in the experimental and control groups yields $F(1,297) = 280.64$ with $p = 0.000$ less than 0.05 level of significance and η^2 partial = 0.637 implies 63.7% variance explained. That is, there is a significant difference between mean interest ratings of students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional strategy and those taught using conventional method as measured by CEIS. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Research Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean interest ratings of male and female NCE II students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy.

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Experimental Group male and female NCE II Students in Citizenship Education Interest Scale (CEIS)

Source	Type III Sum of sq.	df	Mean sq.	F	Sig.	Partial Eta sq.
Corr Model	2.583 ^a	2	1.3065	.7010	.4263	.019
Intercept	286.114	1	286.114	128.76	.000	.755
Pre-CEIS	2.583	1	2.583	1.403	.233	.021
Gender	.000	1	.000	.000	.878	.000

Error	160.311	137	2.114
Total	60028.000	140	
Corrected Total	160.112	139	

R Squared =0.21 (Adjusted R. Squared =.009)

Table 4 shows that the analysis of variance of mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Citizenship Education in the experimental group yields $F(1,137) = 0.00$ with $p = .878$ less than 0.05 level of significance and η^2 partial = 0.000 . The result shows a very high extent in both male and female students' interest in Citizenship Education among the experimental group. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean interest ratings of male and female students taught Citizenship Education using Collaborative Instructional Strategy as measured in CEIS is not rejected. The students' interest in Citizenship Education using the Collaborative instructional strategy was not based on gender

Discussion

This study reveals that the use of collaborative instructional strategy in teaching Citizenship Education improved students' interest during the period of this study. The improvement was statistically significant. The findings are in agreement with Adekola (2014) who maintained that the use of collaborative instructional strategy could enhance the students' interest.

The study also shows that the use of Collaborative Instructional strategy in teaching Citizenship Education improved both male and female students' interest. There was no significant gender difference in students' interest. The result was in consonance with Ayuba (2017) who found that there was no significant difference in interest and retention of male and female students taught a unit of instruction. The findings of this study indicate that the use of Collaborative Instructional Strategy is very effective in closing the gender gap in students' interest in Citizenship Education. Similarly, the findings corroborated that of Azih and Nwosu (2011) whose findings showed that modern teaching methods were superior to conventional method in improving the interest of both male and female students. The findings of this study supported that of Sabiru (2014) who investigated the effects of collaborative learning on Chemistry Students' Interest in balancing of chemical equations in secondary schools in Katsina Metropolis and found that students taught using collaborative learning achieved significantly higher and their anxiety was low when compared with those taught with lecture method. However, the findings of this study on the effects of gender on interest disagreed with the result of Adekola (2014) who found that male students had higher mean interest ratings than their female counterparts when exposed to collaborative learning in reading comprehension.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- i. GSE lecturers should be trained on the use of Collaborative Instructional Strategy for effective teaching and learning of Citizenship Education.

- ii. The management of Colleges of Education should keep abreast of innovative learning strategies, hold subsequent seminars and in-service training for the academic staff members.
- iii. Educational policy makers are expected to use the information provided by this study as a base taking decision on the appropriate instructional strategy like Collaborative instructional strategy to be adopted in Colleges of Education.

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